

CADMIUM IN BULGARIAN GROUNDWATER: AN OVERVIEW

Simeon Valtchev¹, Aglaida Toteva¹, Alexander Grigorov² and Aleksey Benderev¹

¹Geological Institute, Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, Acad. G. Bonchev str., bl. 24, 1113 Sofia. E-mail: simeonvaltscheff@abv.bg; aglaya.j@abv.bg; alekseybenderev@yahoo.com

²Elatsite-Med AD, Mirkovo 2086, Bulgaria. E-mail: a.grigorov@ellatzite-med.com

ABSTRACT: Cadmium is a trace element in groundwater, which has higher mobility compared to other heavy metals due to its ability to form soluble complexes. It is highly toxic in elevated concentrations, has a tendency to accumulate in organisms, and is classified as carcinogenic. Cadmium and its compounds are listed as priority hazardous substances in the EU Water Framework Directive. Sources of an elevated Cd content in groundwater can be natural and anthropogenic. Regarding the latter, recent research has shown a very high leaching potential of Cd from cadmium tellurite (CdTe), which is increasingly being applied in photovoltaic solar cells, and there is concern about the potential risk to the environment and human health. The purpose of this work is to review the available data on background Cd concentrations in groundwater in Bulgaria and present an overview as a reference and basis for the evaluation of future influences. Background Cd concentrations are below 0.5 µg/L for groundwater in most geological formations in the country and relatively elevated, between 1 µg/L and 5 µg/L, for groundwater associated with basic and ultrabasic igneous and metamorphic rocks in southern Bulgaria, as well as a limited number of Cenozoic deposits.

Key words: Cadmium, groundwater, background concentration, Bulgaria

INTRODUCTION

Cadmium belongs to the group of most toxic metals (Sokolov 1995) and although its toxicity is not associated with the metal itself, it is classified as Category 2 carcinogen (i.e. may cause cancer) by analogy with its compounds, e.g. fluoride, sulphate, chloride, oxide, and others (EU 2007). In spite of the high toxicity in elevated concentrations (e.g. Medvedev *et al.* 2017), cadmium in microdoses is important for the development of organisms, including humans, e.g. in regulating blood sugar levels. Cadmium enters the human body through ingestion and inhalation and has the tendency to accumulate in certain tissues and organs, especially in the kidneys (Sychev 2018).

Cadmium and its compounds are listed as priority hazardous substances in the EU Water Framework Directive (EC 2000), thus requiring management plans for discharge. For Cd in groundwater, the EU Directive on the protection of groundwater against pollution and deterioration (EC 2006) requires the establishment of threshold values (TV), i.e. quality criteria for pollutants that have been identified as contributing to the characterisation of bodies or groups of bodies of groundwater as being at risk. The TVs applicable to a good chemical status are based on the protection of the groundwater body, taking into account their impact on and interrelationship with associated surface waters and the direct dependence of terrestrial ecosystems and wetlands, and taking into account knowledge of human toxicology and ecotoxicology. Based on their own procedures, many member states have set TVs in the overall range from 0.08 µg/L to 27 µg/L (Kubier *et al.* 2019; EC, 2010), with most TVs being below 5 µg/L interval and the higher TV related to high natural background contents (CIS 2019). The TVs for surface water impacts on groundwater (average concentrations) in the United Kingdom range between 0.054 µg/L and 0.53 µg/L, depending on the degree of impact, while the TV for Cd in protected aquifers for drinking water is set to 3.75 µg/L (WFD 2015). Groundwater quality standards in different countries vary significantly, e.g. 0.5 µg/L in Denmark, but 10 µg/L in Japan (UNEP 2010). The Bulgarian quality standard for Cd in groundwater is set to 5 µg/L (Reg. 1 2007), specified as the concentration that should not be exceeded in order to protect human health and the environment (WA 1999). Cadmium and its compounds are included in the list of hazardous substances and, as such, its direct discharge into groundwater is prohibited (WA 1999). According to the Water Framework Directive, transposed into national legislation through the Water Act, the main instrument for integrated water management is the River Basin Management Plans (RBMPs), aimed at achieving and maintaining good water status. In the current RBMPs 2022-2027, the threshold values for cadmium pollution calculated by the four basin directorates for

individual groundwater bodies are within the range 3.7-5.0 µg/L (DRBD 2024; BSBD 2024; EABD 2024; WABD 2024).

Elevated Cd concentrations in the environment have been recorded in various mining, industrial and urbanised regions around the world, typically associated with mine water discharge, inadequate waste management, metallurgical processes, electroplating, fuel combustion, production and use of phosphate fertilisers, pigments, plastic stabilisers, etc. With the increasing installation of photovoltaic panels on vast areas of land, there is the potential of increased release of Cd in the environment from cadmium telluride (CdTe), a semiconductor used in thin-film photovoltaic cells and electronic components. Experimental investigations (Tammaro *et al.* 2016; Zeng *et al.* 2015) have shown a high leaching potential of CdTe, resulting in Cd concentrations that multiple times exceed the regulatory limits, raising concerns of posing risk to aquatic and terrestrial ecosystems and human health if present in drinking water (Curtin *et al.* 2020).

Cadmium can enter groundwater naturally by dissolution as a result of weathering or natural oxidation of soils and rocks containing ore minerals, most importantly sphalerite, with which greenokite, the only cadmium mineral of significance, is associated. Greenokite, CdS, has been found in the Bulgarian mineral deposits of Sedmochislenitsi in Eastern Stara Planina; Madjarovo, Kupel in Eastern Rhodope Mountains; Asarel in Srednogorie (Kostov *et al.* 2022). Metallic cadmium has been reported in a study of mineral forming processes in Popsko deposit in Eastern Rhodope Mountains (Berkovska *et al.* 1987). Naturally occurring Cd can also be released through dissolution under anthropogenic influence, e.g., oxidation of soils as a result of denitrification of nitrogen fertilisers. Cadmium in groundwater from anthropogenic sources is most often the result of release from phosphate fertilisers and atmospheric deposition, industrial activity, and transport. Because of the formation of soluble complexes with anions, cadmium has increased mobility compared to other heavy metals (e.g. Moore *et al.* 1983, Kubier *et al.* 2019).

An overview of the available data on background Cd concentrations in groundwater in Bulgaria is presented below.

CADMIUM SOURCES AND CONTENT IN GROUNDWATER

Background Cd concentrations in Bulgarian groundwater

Natural background concentrations of trace elements in groundwater from unconfined aquifers were calculated by Shopova *et al.* (1993). The study included the entire area of the country and was based on data for 11 800 hydrochemical analyses of water samples collected outside ore fields and their zones of influence. The majority of the samples were collected in 1980s in relation to the hydrochemical mapping of Bulgaria and include water from wells and springs, as well as small streams in the mountains. The evaluation approach took into account the influence on groundwater quality of the chemical and mineralogical composition of the water-bearing materials by combining the geological formations in Bulgaria into 11 major groups, background concentrations of 17 trace elements for each group were calculated using statistical methods (Kehayov 1993). The values of the trace element concentration were found to be log-normally distributed and the upper limits of the background were determined from the symmetric parts of the generally asymmetric distributions (Shopova *et al.* 1993). Natural background cadmium concentrations in groundwater are summarised for specific water-bearing materials in Bulgaria in Table 1.

In general, the background Cd concentrations in most groundwater on the territory of the country are within the range between 0.1 µg/L and 0.5 µg/L. A higher background concentration of Cd, 3.85 µg/L, was estimated for groundwater associated with basic and ultrabasic igneous and metamorphic rocks found in the eastern part of the Upper Thracian Graben and the eastern Fore-Balkan. The background Cd concentration for groundwater in volcanic sedimentary formations was not calculated because of unattainable detection limits of the analytical methods used at the time.

Table 1. Natural background levels of Cd in Bulgarian groundwater.

Estimated Cd background concentration ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	Water-bearing materials
-	<p><i>Volcanic sedimentary formations:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Upper Cretaceous - Srednogorie • Oligocene - Rhodope massif and Southwestern Bulgaria
0.1	Talus, clayey sands and sands of various age
	<p><i>Quartzite, sandstones, conglomerates, schists:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Upper Cretaceous quartzite • Late Jurassic schist - Strandzha • Lower Triassic quartzite and sandstones • Green schist formations • Paleozoic - western and central Stara Planina, Kraishte, Graovo, Sakar, Strandzha
	<p><i>Acidic igneous and metamorphic rocks:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • rhyolite, rhyodacite and dacite – late Palaeogene effusive magmatites in the Rilo-Rhodope massif in southwestern Bulgaria • granite, granodiorite, quartz monzodiorite - South Bulgarian Granitoids, Na-alkaline formations of Stara Planina, Srednogorie neo-intrusive formation in Western Bulgaria • gneiss and schists of the Precambrian Ultrametamorphic Complex
	<p><i>Intermediate igneous and metamorphic rocks:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • latite, trachyte, trachyandesite and andesite - Upper Cretaceous and Late Paleozoic volcanic bodies in Srednogorie and Rilo-Rhodopae massif • diorite, syenite, monzonite, syenomonzodiorite - Rilo-Rhodopean batolite, Na-alkaline formation in Stara Planina, Srednogorie neo-intrusive formation in Eastern Bulgaria
	Marble of Proterozoic age in Central and Western Rhodopes, Southern Pirin, Slavyanka
0.2	Loess and loess-like deposits, loess-covered gravel
	<p><i>Marls, mudstones, siltstones:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Paleogene – Varna Depression; basins of Burgas, Pernik, Kyustendil • Early Cretaceous – Fore-Balkan and Moesian Platform
	<p><i>Limestone and dolomites:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Neogene – Varna • Paleogene – Chirpan • Late Cretaceous – Kotel, Shumen • Early Cretaceous - Northern Bulgaria • Middle Triassic, Late Jurassic - Northwestern and Central Northern Bulgaria, Kraishte, Central Srednogorie, Sakar-Strandzha
0.3	Alluvial and alluvial-proluvial deposits
0.5	<p><i>Flysch and flysch-like deposits:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Late Jurassic and Early Cretaceous - Kraishte, Stara Planina, Western Fore-Balkan, North Bulgaria, Strandzha • Early Jurassic, Late Cretaceous, Paleogene - Eastern Stara Planina • Upper Eocene - Eastern Rhodope
	<p><i>Basic and ultra-basic igneous and metamorphic rocks:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gabbro, diorite, pyroxenite, peridotite – Srednogorie • Basalt, andesite in early Paleozoic volcanic bodies; • Serpentinites and amphibolites of the Precambrian Ultrametamorphic Complex
	3.8

Groundwater monitoring data for cadmium in Bulgaria

The National System for Environmental Monitoring (NSEM) provides information about the condition of the components of the environment. It is managed by the Executive Environment Agency (ExEA), which maintains regional and national databases. The condition of the water resources is assessed

at basin level by the four Basin Directorates – Danube Region (DRBD), Black Sea Region (BSBD), East Aegean Sea (EABD) and West Aegean Sea (WABD).

Groundwater quality monitoring is carried out in a network for operational and control monitoring, consisting of 519 points to observe the chemical state of groundwater, including monitoring points in the source protection zones for drinking water. The water sampling and chemical analyses are conducted by 15 regional laboratories of ExEA. Cadmium is listed in the group ‘Specific Groundwater Contaminants – Metals and Metalloids’ with a monitoring frequency of 1, 2 or 4 times per year, depending on the monitoring purpose– operational or control type. In 2023, a total of 350 samples from 258 monitoring points were analysed for cadmium with detection limits either 0.1 µg/L (272 samples), or 0.3 µg/L (78 samples), depending on different laboratory capabilities. The NSEM monitoring network, the areas of the four basin directorates and the 2023 testing for cadmium in groundwater are shown in Figure 1. Cadmium concentrations above detection limits were reported for 9 samples. The maximum concentration of 0.6 µg/L was measured in karst water from the Golo Bardo basin in Western Bulgaria. In the same region, exceedances of the detection limits were reported in groundwater in metamorphic rocks (0.4 µg/L and 0.3 µg/L) and Quaternary-Neogene sediments (0.3 µg/L and 0.2 µg/L). The rest of the detections were in the range between 0.1 µg/L and 0.3 µg/L in Quaternary aquifers, three in the northwestern Danube plane and in one sample in the Zlatitsa-Pirdop basin, to the south of the region of intrusive rocks from the Late Cretaceous. All reported Cd concentrations in groundwater from the monitoring network correspond well to the background concentrations shown in Table 1.

Figure 1. Monitoring points of National System for Environmental Monitoring and Cd testing in 2023 across the areas of the four Basin Directorates: DRBD - Danube region, BSBD - Black Sea region, EABD-East Aegean, WABD –West Aegean region

For the purposes of their river basin management plans, each basin directorate has calculated background Cd concentrations for all 169 individual groundwater bodies distinguished on the territory of Bulgaria. In general, in almost all groundwater bodies, background Cd concentrations are within the range 0.06 µg/L - 0.6 µg/L, with several exceptions between 1.0 µg/L and 5.0 µg/L for aquifers including: one Quaternary colluvium deposit in the Danube region (DRBD 2024) and one alluvium deposit in the Black Sea catchment (BSBD 2024); six karst bodies in the Rila-Rhodope region and six bodies in fractured igneous and metamorphic rocks in Southern Bulgaria, as well as two Quaternary and one Neogene

deposits in the Pirin region (EABD 2024; WABD 2024). The background concentrations were calculated as the 50th percentile of the value distribution of the reported Cd concentrations or half the detection limit, if not detected (CIWM, 2009).

Concerning anthropogenic impact on groundwater, regulatory agencies do not publish data systematically. EABD published data for the period 2010-2012 only, from internal groundwater monitoring by site owners, indicating Cd contamination on the sites of two industrial facilities and one municipality, where Cd concentrations between 5 µg/L and 306 µg/L were reported, as well as data from the site of a smelter, where Cd concentrations > 1 mg/L were repeatedly recorded, with a maximum value in one of the monitoring wells exceeding 10 mg/L (EABD 2024).

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

Estimates of background cadmium concentrations in groundwater in Bulgaria are available for generalised groups of water-bearing materials, as well as for all individual groundwater bodies. The available data are consistent, showing that the unconfined groundwater in most geological formations in the country has background concentrations of Cd below 0.5 µg/L. In certain geological environments, Cd content in groundwater is relatively elevated and the estimated background concentrations are within the range between 1 µg/L and 5 µg/L. These are generally associated with basic and ultrabasic igneous and metamorphic rocks in Southern Bulgaria, as well as a limited number of Quaternary and Neogene deposits. This is also generally consistent with data from other regions in the world, e.g. Kubier *et al.* (2019) mention summarised background cadmium concentrations in groundwater in Germany, ranging from 0.1 µg/L in loess aquifers below arable land to 2.7 µg/L in sandy aquifers below forested lands, with typical values being below 0.1 µg/L in Palaeozoic, Triassic and Jurassic aquifers, and reaching more than 1 µg/L in Permian, Cretaceous and Cenozoic formations. The same authors also refer to mean Cd background levels of 0.2 µg/L overall to 0.5 µg/L in non-calcareous sediments in Ireland (Tedd *et al.* 2017) and below 1 µg/L based on analyses from over 3,000 wells in the United States (Ayotte *et al.* 2011).

The 2023 data from the National System for Environmental Monitoring show that the concentrations in groundwater were below 1 µg/L in all 258 locations monitored for Cd, in addition they were below 0.3 µg/L in approximately 98% of the monitored locations.

The available data on background concentrations of Cd in groundwater provides an adequate reference and useful basis for the assessment of future influences on groundwater quality as a result of cadmium release from potential new sources, e.g. cadmium telluride, which is increasingly being applied in electronic components and thin-film photovoltaic cells.

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